

DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRONIC RESOURCES IN THE COURSE OF AUTOMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES

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Annotation: *This article deals with the development and implementation of automation systems directly in production processes, including research, design and installation, as well as the development of e-learning resources.*

Key words: *technological processes, machine-building enterprises, high-precision and robust, modern production, automatic systems, electronic educational resources*

The problems to be solved in the automation of production processes of modern production are the knowledge of specialists on the principles of construction and operation of various automation devices, methods of creating different types and classes of automated systems, as well as general technical it also requires mastering the language. This should be expressed in a language that is equally understandable to professionals dealing with the installation, configuration and operation of automation systems in a logically considered and technically based system of automation of a technological process. At the same time, all specialists should have a unified understanding of the equipment of the automation system, the implementation of the given rules of adjustment, methods of installation of instruments and automation, transmission of pulse and command lines and source lines.

In the process of modern engineering, it is possible to understand the set of activities that carry out the production of certain machines, equipment, hardware and other products in the production process.

The production process involves a wide range of issues related to different types of production, different technological processes, computer calculations, various elements of the production process.

A machine-building enterprise is a complex that ensures the uninterrupted operation of all elements of the production process. In mechanical engineering, the production process consists of three main stages: supply, processing, and assembly. There are zagotova workshops for procurement, where various technological processes are carried out.

The main volume of processing is carried out in machine-building enterprises. Heat treatment between individual processing operations is carried out at specialized heat plants or at heat treatment plants with the help of appropriate machines. In the assembly shops, the finished parts are mounted on the mechanism and equipment, assembled one by one on the basis of the technological process. They are inspected after each assembly.

In recent years, extensive work has been done to automate control and assembly processes, and to create control-assembly and automated lines. Automation of these processes will allow, first of all, to improve the quality of products produced in large manufacturing industries (vacuum devices, radio elements, hardware, etc.), as well as to automate control and assembly. The control and assembly of finished products involves more workers than their production.

Although automation is produced in enterprises with a mass character of products, the increase in the range of products allows them to use more and more flexible automated systems in serial enterprises.

Equipment equipped with software control is also being used effectively in serial production conditions. Mechanization is only inefficient. Automation of loading and unloading operations. Similarly, these products are used to transport interdepartmental and domestic vehicles, as well as to accumulate and expend mutual operational reserves.

In order to improve the quality of project documentation, reduce their volume and duration, the design of technological process automation systems should be based on instructional and normative materials that incorporate advanced industry experience in the field of automation, as well as normative materials of general industrial and sectoral nature. When designing technological automation systems, it is necessary to make maximum use of standard designs, solutions, constructions, etc.

The schematic diagram of automation is the main technical document of the project, which shows the level and principle of automation of the technological device. This reflects all the key decisions made at the initial stage of building a management system. The drawing should provide an understanding of the control object, the tools used in control, adjustment, program control, signaling, blocking, protection and automation. Usually alarm, blocking and protection are extended in special drawings. The schematic diagrams show the scheme of the technological device, along with the control bodies and communications, the means of automation, the schematics of the interaction between the various devices of the technological units and the means of automation.

Automation problems are solved using technological means, which include selected devices, means of identifying primary information, means of information exchange and processing, means of presentation and output of information to service personnel, and auxiliary means.

REFERENCES:

1. Yusupbekov N.R. and others. "Technological process control systems", Tashkent, 1997.
2. Yusupbekov N.R. and others. "Automation and automation of production processes." - Tashkent, 1982.
3. Mansurov X.N. "Automation and automation of production processes", Tashkent 1987.